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THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS

Abstract. Increasing the motivation of students is the main task of the teacher. As we know there are two types of motivation: internal and external. The basis of internal motivation is the interests, needs of the student. At this time, the student does not need to be encouraged or punished. The achievement of the goal occurs in the footsteps of one's own interests and skills. And during extrinsic motivation, the student expects encouragement, reward (good score, praise, gift from a parent, etc.) for the completed task). Studies prove that the way to increase motivation in students is to create a positive atmosphere in the classroom. Creating a positive atmosphere involves an attitude towards students, listening to students, understanding, considering their opinion, courtesy, humor, justice, etc. There are always students who find mathematics a dry, boring, difficult subject. Therefore, our goal is to help students overcome difficulties and show them the attractive side of mathematics. And this will happen if the teaching will be student-oriented.

Key words: motivation, mathematics, teaching

Анотація. Підвищення мотивації учнів є основним завданням вчителя. Як відомо, існує два види мотивації: внутрішня та зовнішня. В основі внутрішньої мотивації лежать інтереси, потреби учня. За таких умов учня не треба ні заохочувати, ні карати. Досягнення мети відбувається шляхом реалізації власних інтересів та умінь. А за зовнішньої мотивації учень очікує заохочення, винагороди (хороша оцінка, похвала, подарунок від батьків тощо) за виконане завдання тощо). Дослідження доводять, шлях підвищення мотивації в учнів полягає у створенні позитивної атмосфери в класі. Створення позитивної атмосфери передбачає ставлення до учнів, вислуховування здобувачів освіти, розуміння, думки, ввічливість, гумор, справедливість тощо. Завжди є учні, які знаходять математику сухим, нудним та важким предметом. Тому наша мета – допомогти учням подолати труднощі та показати їм привабливу сторону математики. І це станеться, якщо викладання буде орієнтоване на учня.

Ключові слова: мотивація, математика, викладання

If we look at the “TIMSS” (international study of mathematics and Natural Sciences) studies, we will see that the situation in Georgia is not very favorable in terms of teaching mathematics. Georgia first participated in these studies in 2007. These studies are conducted every four years in Georgia. According to these studies in 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, the results of 4th and 8th graders in mathematics are as follows:

years	Number of participating countries Class 4	Average score	Georgia score	Number of participating countries Class 8c	Average score	Georgia score
2007	43	500	438	56	500	410
2011	50	500	450	42	500	431
2015	49	500	463	39	500	453
2019	58	500	482	39	500	461

TIMESSE_ research shows that Georgian students are internationally scaled they have below average achievements in both 4th and 8th grades. It should also be noted that in 2015–2019, the results have improved, albeit insignificantly.

Why is there such a low result in mathematics? Because the motivation to teach this subject is low. Human behavior is determined by motivation. Motivation has a significant impact on the formation of the personality, its activities, interests, attitudes. Motivation is the most important factor in educational activity.

Increasing the motivation of students is the main task of the teacher. As we know there are two types of motivation: internal and external. The basis of internal motivation is the interests, needs of the student. At this time, the student does not need to be encouraged or punished. The achievement of the goal occurs in the footsteps of one's own interests and skills. And during extrinsic motivation, the student expects encouragement, reward (good score, praise, gift from a parent, etc.) for the completed task).

Students with intrinsic motivation tend to be more responsible for learning. They are not afraid of difficult tasks. They have good self-esteem. They are confident that they can complete a difficult task. They are ready to deepen their knowledge. Believing in success. When motivation is External, the student tries to avoid a difficult task. It is unacceptable to use factors that cause external motivation for a long time. In such a case, it is impossible to achieve significant success. A learning activity that is conditioned only by a good omen, a gift, etc. There is nothing for the student. For a student, learning itself should be important, and not a reward, praise, a good score, with which he will approve of himself among friends, parents. As soon as the student does not have the mentioned mechanisms of motivation, his interest in learning disappears. However, we do not say that extrinsic motivation should be ignored during teaching. The teacher must take into account both internal and external motivation of the student during teaching. It should not rely only on internal motivation of the student, or vice versa, only on external motivation. D. Uznadze believed that true learning is possible only in conditions of cognitive interest, thirst for knowledge, and therefore intrinsic motivation. The humanistic interpretation of motivation emphasizes such internal sources of motivation as the need for self-actualization of the personality (Maslow) and the tendency to self-actualization (Rogers). Representatives of

humanistic psychology mainly focus on the student's personal development and attach less importance to such a teaching style, focused only on obtaining knowledge and which is reflected in the test results. They believe that a person should have the experience of success, not failure, and learning should proceed through discoveries.

Studies prove that the way to increase motivation in students is to create a positive atmosphere in the classroom. Creating a positive atmosphere involves an attitude towards students, listening to students, understanding, considering their opinion, courtesy, humor, justice, etc. The learning process should be related to the student's interests and positive emotions. In this case, learning becomes a means of satisfying the interests and curiosity of the student. In this case, the learning process will not be forced, but fun. We, teachers, must bear in mind that every person has a desire to succeed. Therefore, we must create a learning environment where students will not be afraid of failure. Here it already depends on the teacher how much he will be able to interest the students. The greater the degree of learning, the more motivated students are. Studies show that students' interest in learning is greater the more organized the course of study. Modern education is such an education when the priority is student and result-oriented education. We need to understand what our students need. It is their interests that should be taken into account when planning the educational process. We have to offer students tasks that do not exceed their capabilities and will be impossible for them. So, we stimulate them, strengthen faith in ourselves. We should try to involve every student in the learning process, because passivity slows down the motivation and curiosity of students. If the student is passive, his curiosity is slowed down, he has no interest in the subject-learning mathematics, that is, we do not work well, do not create a suitable environment for him, we do not show the student the need to study mathematics, we do not use appropriate activities. National curriculum Chapter III. In Article 10, a student-centered approach, we read: "learning should take place in a positive and orderly environment, where positive relationships and interactions are of particular importance, where the student is valued, recognized and, together with the teacher, is responsible for his / her learning and development". As we can see, one of the main tasks of the national curriculum is to create a positive environment for students. Also, according to the national curriculum, the school should offer students a multilevel learning process, which implies the use of many methods, strategies, ways of solving problems or types of activities. We can say that the goal of the teacher is to increase students' motivation and interest in learning through various activities.

The teacher should contribute to the emergence of internal motivation in students, its maintenance through external mechanisms. As we said, Praise is an extrinsic motivation mechanism. But praise should not be superficial, only for "praise". Praise should be specific, guttural. It should be accompanied by constructive advice. Praise is ineffective if the teacher uses invariable expressions. For example: "Well done", "good"... The teacher should not

compare students with each other, should not cause competition between students. Students should appreciate every effort and effort. It turned out that motivation is individual.

People differ from each other in the degree of motivation, in terms of its strength. Motivation is not innate and immutable. Motivation is dynamic and depends on age, environmental factors. Behaviorists focus on external motives such as praise and reward. In their opinion, if we constantly encourage students for a particular behavior, they will develop a certain type of behavior. According to the behaviorist approach, praise provides the student with information about his achievements, which is important for motivation. Praise creates a positive attitude for the student to perform the task. Motivation is a tool that allows us to achieve high teaching efficiency. However, building a lesson in such a way as to meet the motivational expectations of all students in the class is quite difficult. There are always students who find mathematics a dry, boring, difficult subject. Therefore, our goal is to help students overcome difficulties and show them the attractive side of mathematics. And this will happen if the teaching will be student-oriented. In the process of teaching do not forget and always remember:

- The student plays an active role in the learning process, while the teacher is only the head, the facilitator of learning;
- Involve students in a variety of activities that promote problem solving, discovery learning, sharing ideas, analyzing, drawing conclusions;
- Students are independent, responsible for their learning, they choose how and when to do it;
- Teaching is based on collaboration;
- Reflexive approach to the quality of teaching and learning process is used.

We will be able to increase the motivation of our students towards mathematics and not only mathematics. This will facilitate the teaching process.

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